

2024 NNLM ACTIVE MEMBER SURVEY

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

NNLM | National Evaluation Center
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Executive Summary

The 2024 Active Member Survey was the second Network-wide, standard, online survey conducted on behalf of the NNLM.¹ Its purpose was to connect with member organizations who had meaningfully engaged with the Network (from May 1, 2023 to April 30, 2024) and to compile feedback on their perceptions of the value and benefits of their membership; their awareness and usage of NNLM services; interests in trainings and funding, as well as to learn more about their own organizational characteristics. Below is a brief summary of its main findings by section.

A. Benefits & Value of NNLM Membership: *Member organizations are highly satisfied with their membership.*

- The single most important reason to join NNLM as rank-ordered by survey respondents was training opportunities (38%) in first place, followed by funding opportunities (21%) in second and free informational materials (17%) in third place.
- Member organizations were most aware of the Network’s free informational materials (91%), funding opportunities (82%), and training opportunities (82%).
- There is high satisfaction with the NNLM membership as noted by an aggregate satisfaction index score of 81.7 (out of 100).²
- 80% of survey respondents are highly or very highly likely to recommend NNLM membership to other organizations.

B. Communications: *The NNLM message is best conveyed to its membership directly through NNLM communications.*

- Almost all member organizations (92%) hear about the Network through NNLM communications (e.g., email, blog, newsletter or listserv).
- Similarly, nearly all survey respondents have regular, uninterrupted internet/broadband (94%), technical skills to engage in online classes and services (92%), and access and technology to meet their needs (84%).
- Lack of time was the single most important barrier to further engagement with the NNLM (59%), followed by lack of staffing (25%).

C. Training and Education: *Training continues to be the most valued NNLM service, with a special focus on workforce development.*

- At least two-thirds of survey respondents expressed interest in future trainings focused on education/training and workforce development (71%), health disparity/health equity (70%), and health and health information (66%).
- In terms of types of training desired by member organizations for future NNLM trainings, survey respondents selected: NLM product training (66%), beginner-level training on special topics (58%), and skills training (58%).

¹ The survey (an “establishment survey”) collected data from member organizations and not individuals. It was a single-round, self-administered, cross-sectional census of all member organizations that were actively engaged with the NNLM during Grant Year 3 (n=1,068). Analysis is drawn from the 344 member organizations who submitted a response.

² The NEC Satisfaction Index Score is the composite of 3 survey items: expectations met, comparison to ideal, and overall satisfaction.

- A majority (58%) of member organizations expressed interest in more trainings on data science topics, and artificial intelligence (AI) emerged as the topic of greatest interest.
- D. Funding:** *There is high awareness about NNLM funding opportunities, with a majority preferring smaller-sized awards.*
- Respondents indicated a high awareness of NNLM funding opportunities (86% of survey respondents).
 - Only one-third (33%) of active member organizations had applied to NNLM funding in the last three years (2021-2024).
 - The minimum level of funding needed to make applying appealing was ranked as follows: \$1,000 (30%), \$5,000 (21%), and \$10,000 (13%).
 - Of the 12% of survey respondents who are not interested in applying, some of their reasons include not having people/space for new projects (38%), not having staff/time for application process (30%), and NNLM funding areas do not align with member organization's mission (27%).
- E. Organizational Profile:** *Most respondents come from large member organizations where Spanish is the most common language, besides English.*
- The top three member organization types among survey respondents were: academic health sciences library (25%), public library (18%), and hospital library (17%).
 - While 38% of the member organizations use "English only" to communicate with their service communities, Spanish (60%) is the most common language besides English.
 - Most active member organizations that responded were from very large organizations (more than 30 staff members, 33%), followed by medium (6 to 15 staff members, 23%).
 - A majority (61%) of member organizations provide services to students, faculty, and staff at higher education institutions.

Group Comparisons: *NEC compared the 2022 and 2024 responses on all items that appeared in both surveys to identify any differences that achieved statistical significance.³ Compared to the 2022 survey respondents, the 2024 respondents were significantly more likely to have:*

- identified free informational materials, training opportunities, funding opportunities, and information/resources available as reasons to join NNLM;
- reported awareness of free informational materials, funding opportunities, continuing education credit from MLA, CNE, or CHES, NLM traveling exhibitions, and MLA specializations;
- indicated, on average, significantly higher levels of satisfaction on each of the four (4) core satisfaction battery items (meet expectations, comparison to ideal, likelihood to recommend, and overall satisfaction) as well as the aggregate satisfaction index score;

³ Based on standard, best practices, we defined statistical significance as p-values at or below 0.05, which indicates group differences for particular survey items that would have occurred by chance alone at or less than 5% of the time. Additional statistical comparisons may be described in future supplemental reports.

- selected lack of time as a top 3 barrier for engagement with NNLM (and were less likely to have identified [being] unsure of how to become more engaged with NNLM); and
- identified education/training and workforce development and data driven research/culture as topics of interest for future NNLM trainings.

NEC's Recommendations for the Future: *Continue investing in Data Quality and a rigorous, biennial NNLM Active Member Survey.*

Based on the 2022 and 2024 member survey experiences, NEC recommends that the Network:

- Continues to prioritize membership record cleanup, maintenance, and data quality processes (especially record completeness and validation) for the NNLM membership directory;
- Reengages NNLM ROCs in a coordinated communications and promotion strategy before and after future survey deployments;
- Maintains the rigor and frequency of the NNLM Active Member Survey in future cooperative agreements; and
- Establishes compliance mechanisms for a “regional survey blackout” to avoid proximity and/or overlap with future Network-wide surveys.